

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Project short name PlasticTrace

Project full title Metrological traceability of measurement data from nano- to small-microplastics for a greener environment and food safety

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Confidentiality Status:
PU - Public, fully open

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Data Management Plan

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METROLOGY PARTNERSHIP |

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1 Data management plan

1.1 Data summary

Questions	Answers
1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use them for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	<p>This project used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confidential data • Internal data from the participants • Publicly available data <p>These data were used for the following purpose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of the project's results
2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	The data/research outputs generated were from measurements, calibrations, comparisons and validation studies. The project collected the following types of data: images in JPEG format, numerical data in CSV and txt, models/algorithms in py and mat format, word templates for SOPs/protocols, text description data in Markdown format
3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<p><i>Purpose of the data generation or re-use</i></p> <p>The data generated and re-used were from measurements, calibrations, comparisons and validations. They were used in meeting the project's objectives and in conference and peer-reviewed publications.</p> <p><i>Data generated in relation to the objectives of the project</i></p> <p>Data were generated by the consortium in order to meet objectives 1 - 4. Measurement and calibration data resulted from objectives 1 and 3 and comparison and validation data from objectives 2, 3 and 4. Data from questionnaires and market surveys were used to support end-user uptake (objective 5).</p> <p><i>Data re-used in relation to the objectives of the project</i></p> <p>Measurement, calibration, comparison and validation data were re-used by the consortium in order to meet objectives 1 and 4.</p> <p>The project has collected/generated 10 datasets so far. The reasons for their collection/generation are specified below:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <p>1. Development of innovative antioxidant food packaging systems based on natural extracts from food industry waste and Moringa oleifera leaves (Dataset 1).</p> <p>The dataset was collected in order to evaluate the fabrication and characterization of sustainable cellulose-based active packaging using food-industry waste and natural extracts as antioxidant agents. These systems are promising for industrial applications and more sustainable farm-to-fork food production systems.</p> <p>These data mainly contribute to the objectives 1, 2, 3 and 5. This dataset was used to produce the analysis and conclusions for the publication G. Barzan et al., Food Chemistry 432 (2023) 13708. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12613873</p> <p>2. Optics miniaturization strategy for demanding Raman spectroscopy applications (Dataset 2)</p> <p>The dataset was collected in order to evaluate the performance of a centimeter-scale miniaturization of a Raman spectrometer using cheap non-stabilized laser diodes, densely packed optics, and non-cooled small sensors.</p>

These data mainly contribute to the objectives 3 and 5. This dataset was used to produce the analysis and conclusions for the publication O. Ilchenko et al., Nat Commun 15, 3049 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.23712891>

3. Data Non-invasive Real-Time Monitoring of Bacterial Activity by NCIS (Dataset 3)

The dataset was collected in order to evaluate reliable, real-time measurements of bacterial activity using non-contact impedance spectroscopy and to validate its performance against traditional analytical methods.

These data mainly contribute to the objectives 3 and 5. This dataset was used to produce the analysis and conclusions for the publication Thirstrup, C., et al. (2025). Sensors, 25(8), 2427. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15186864>

4. Accuracy assessment of a micro-Raman spectroscopy method for small microplastic particles in infant milk formula (Dataset 4)

The dataset was collected in order to evaluate Accuracy assessment of a micro-Raman spectroscopy method for small microplastic particles in infant milk formula.

These data mainly contribute to the objectives 1, 2, 4 and 5. This dataset was used to produce the analysis and conclusions for the publication Putzu, M., et al. (2025). Talanta Open, 12, 100586. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17483289>

5. Tracking Nanoplastics in Drinking Water: A New Frontier with the combination of Dielectrophoresis and Raman Spectroscopy/Dataset (Dataset 5)

The dataset was collected in order to demonstrate the hyphenation of Dielectrophoresis and Raman Spectroscopy for the characterization of nanoplastics in drinking water.

These data mainly contribute to the objectives 1, 3, and 5. This dataset was used to produce the analysis and conclusions for the publication Fadda, M., et al. Micropl.&Nanopl. 5, 24 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14762447>

6. Inter-instrument definition of valid criteria for the automatic identification of microplastics by micro-Raman spectroscopy (Dataset 6)

This dataset presents all Raman spectra used to create an automatic identification tool for PET particles, match determination data, match performance data, a user-friendly MS Excel spreadsheet for automatic PET identification and a video tutorial for said spreadsheet.

These data mainly contribute to the objectives 1, 2, 3 and 5. This dataset was used to produce the analysis and conclusions for the

	<p>publication Fernandes, R., et al. (2025). Talanta, 298(Pt A), 128834. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17079480</p> <p>7. Characterizing nanoplastic suspensions of increasing complexity: inter-laboratory comparison of size measurements using dynamic light scattering (Dataset 7)</p> <p>This dataset presents all raw data from an Inter-laboratory comparison of size measurements using dynamic light scattering for nanoplastics characterization in different media. These data mainly contribute to the objectives 1, 2, 3,4 and 5. This dataset was used to produce the analysis and conclusions for the publication Altmann, K., et al. (2025). Environmental Science: Nano. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17105630</p> <p>8. Applicability of the novel methodology to multi-parameter characterisation of SMPs (< 10 µm) and NPs (< 0.1 µm) (Dataset 8)</p> <p>This dataset corresponds to the characterisation of nanopolypropylene suspensions in water using the following techniques to measure size distribution, number concentration and mass fraction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Light Scattering techniques (DLS, MADLS) - size distribution • Fractionation techniques hyphenated to Static Light Scattering (FFF-MALS) - size distribution • Particle Tracking Analysis (PTA) - number concentration • Thermoanalytical techniques (Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS) - mass fraction <p>For each technique, raw data are provided together with the corresponding measurement protocol. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17712080</p> <p>9. Optimization of tablet processing as a reference material for microplastic detection methods (Dataset 9)</p> <p>This is the dataset of Optimization of tablet processing as a reference material for microplastic detection methods https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15880120</p> <p>10. Interlaboratory Comparison Reveals State of the Art in Microplastic Detection and Quantification Methods - Supporting Information (Dataset 10)</p> <p>This file contains the Supporting Information associated with the publication “Interlaboratory comparison reveals state-of-the-art in microplastic detection and quantification methods”. Anal. Chem. 2025, 97, 16, 8719–8728. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17989943</p>
4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The estimated overall size of the data/research outputs is expected to be in the range: 10 GB 1 TB.

<p>5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?</p>	<p><i>Data generated in the project</i> The data generated were from measurements, calibrations, comparisons and validations. The data collected from domestic properties remain confidential and are not included in the repository. The project has collected/generated 9 datasets. The origin for their collection/generation are specified below:</p> <p>Dataset 1: Experimental data originates from experimental equipment Dataset 2: Experimental data originates from experimental equipment Dataset 3: Experimental data originates from experimental equipment Dataset 4: Experimental data originates from experimental equipment Dataset 5: Experimental data originates from experimental equipment Dataset 6: Experimental data originates from experimental equipment Dataset 7: Experimental data originates from experimental equipment Dataset 8: Experimental data originates from experimental equipment Dataset 9: Experimental data originates from experimental equipment Dataset 10: Experimental data originates from experimental equipment</p> <p><i>Re-used data</i> The existing data originate from several sources, which include: participant's pre-existing data, data from the scientific literature, real-world measurement data and data from simulation experiments.</p>
<p>6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?</p>	<p>The data were suitable for use by other research groups working on the following topics: microplastics, nanoplastics, environmental pollution/monitoring, food safety, food packaging, (bio) plastics manufacturing. It was also useful for standards committees including ISO/TC 147/SC 2/JWG1 <i>ISO Joint Working Group on plastics in waters and related matrices</i>, CEN/TC 352/WG1 <i>CEN Technical Committee on Nanotechnologies/Measurement and Characterisation and performance evaluation</i>, ISO/TC 334 <i>ISO Technical Committee on reference materials (previously known as ISO/REMCO)</i>, EURAMET TC-MC <i>EURAMET technical committee on Metrology in Chemistry</i>, CCQM (OAWG) <i>OAWG is the Organic Analysis Working Group of CCQM</i>, VAMAS TWA 45 <i>VAMAS on Micro and Nano Plastics in the Environment</i>, ASTM E56.02 <i>Standardisation in Nanotechnology - Physical and Chemical Characterisation</i>.</p> <p>The data might be useful to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders from industry • Standardisation bodies • NMIs/Dis • Other scientists working in the field of risk assessment and (eco) toxicology • Decision makers <p>The project has collected/generated 9 datasets. Their use is specified</p>

	<p>below:</p> <p>Dataset 1: Data generated during the project could be useful for the scientific community, metrological community, industrial stakeholders and R&D sector.</p> <p>Dataset 2: Data generated during the project could be useful for the scientific community, metrological community, industrial stakeholders and R&D sector.</p> <p>Dataset 3: Data generated during the project could be useful for the scientific community, metrological community, industrial stakeholders and R&D sector.</p> <p>Dataset 4: Data generated during the project could be useful for the scientific community, metrological community, industrial stakeholders and R&D sector.</p> <p>Dataset 5: Data generated during the project could be useful for the scientific community, metrological community, industrial stakeholders and R&D sector.</p> <p>Dataset 6: Data generated during the project could be useful for the scientific community, metrological community, industrial stakeholders and R&D sector.</p> <p>Dataset 7: Data generated during the project could be useful for the scientific community, metrological community, industrial stakeholders and R&D sector.</p> <p>Dataset 8: Data generated during the project could be useful for the scientific community, metrological community, industrial stakeholders and R&D sector.</p> <p>Dataset 9: Data generated during the project could be useful for the scientific community, metrological community, industrial stakeholders and R&D sector.</p> <p>Dataset 10: Data generated during the project could be useful for the scientific community, metrological community, industrial stakeholders and R&D sector.</p>
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1.2 Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) Data

1.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Questions	Answers
7 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?	<p>Yes, each of the project's deposited datasets were identified by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Commit/tag on Git repository • Handle • Other
8 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata were created? What disciplinary or general standards were followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata were created and how.	<p>The metadata created for all of the project's deposited datasets were open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); the European Partnership on Metrology funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their</p>

	<p>organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.</p> <p>Data generated in the project and published in open access are discoverable with metadata according to the FAIR principles. Parts of the data produced at time of generation not fulfil all FAIR requirements but can be upgraded to these by means of reprocessing.</p> <p>The project's 10 datasets are all available on Zenodo. Therefore, they are discoverable with the following metadata: 1) description, 2) creator / ownership, 3) access, 4) lifestyle, 5) persistent identifiers.</p>
9 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?	Yes, the following search keywords were provided in the metadata to optimise the discovery and potential re-use of the deposited datasets: calibration, traceability, polymer name, mass concentration, size, spectroscopy, number concentration
10 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Zenodo complies with FAIR principles (https://about.zenodo.org/principles/). The metadata are indexed in a searchable resource. Metadata are licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata are exported via Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) and can be harvested.

1.2.2 Making data accessible

Questions	Answers
Repository:	
11 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	<p>The data and associated metadata, documentation and code were deposited in the trusted open access repository Zenodo (https://zenodo.org) or other trusted repositories located using the Registry of Research Data Repositories https://www.re3data.org/.</p> <p>The project has collected/generated 9 datasets. They are deposited as follow:</p> <p>Dataset 1: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12613873</p> <p>Dataset 2: https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.23712891</p> <p>Dataset 3: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15186864</p> <p>Dataset 4: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17483289</p> <p>Dataset 5: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14762447</p> <p>Dataset 6: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17079480</p> <p>Dataset 7: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17105630</p> <p>Dataset 8: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17712080</p> <p>Dataset 9: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15880120</p>

Questions	Answers
	Dataset 10: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17989943
12 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data were deposited?	The datasets were uploaded via a standard procedure and require no special arrangements.
13 Does the repository ensure that the data are assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes, Zenodo assigned an identifier (DOI) to each of the project's deposited datasets. The repository resolved the identifier to a digital object.
Data:	
14 Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	<p>All of the data that were needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications were made openly available as the default unless there was a specific reason not to publish the data.</p> <p><i>Datasets which cannot be shared – voluntary restrictions</i> Other data may be made available on a case-by-case basis if it is relevant for third parties. The following data is not publicly available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data obtained with the permission of third parties, but the third parties have not agreed to make the data publicly available. • Data that discloses the identity of a manufacturer. • Data that compromises the protection of a participant(s) intellectual property. <p>The level of data made available was also considered, for example, pre-processed data will not be provided unless there is a clear reason for doing so.</p> <p><i>Datasets which cannot be shared - legal / contractual reasons</i> All of the data from the project was made available, with the exception of market or customer survey data, which are commercially sensitive and cannot be shared.</p>
15 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.	The data used in scientific publications, posters and oral communications were made available for re-use as soon as is reasonably possible. Some of the data are expected to be subject to an embargo period of 18 months whilst a patent application is pending.
16 Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?	Yes, Zenodo provides well described conditions for free and standardised access (see http://about.zenodo.org/policies/). • Data were accessible through Zenodo's REST API https://developers.zenodo.org
17 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	<p>There are no restrictions on the use of the published data, but users were required to acknowledge the project and the source of the data in any resulting publications, according to the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As some data have restricted access, access is only provided after personal contact to the authors via the repository interface

Questions	Answers
18 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	User registration requirements on repositories (e.g. Zenodo) ensure recording of the identities of those accessing the data.
19 Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	No, a data access committee is not necessary because the selection of data to be openly accessible were made on a case by case basis by the partner(s). All partners have been informed and are aware of ethical aspects and data security such as for the protection of IP for any project outputs It may be necessary to withhold all or some of the data generated. This were decided by the relevant partner(s) associated with the respective dataset.
Metadata:	
20 Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	In Zenodo, metadata are licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata are exported via OAI-PMH and can be harvested.
21 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data are no longer available?	The data will remain available and findable for the lifetime of the Zenodo repository, which is expected to be a minimum of 20 years. If data are withdrawn from Zenodo, the DOI and the URL of the original object are retained. In case of closure of the Zenodo repository, best efforts were made by Zenodo to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.
22 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data and will this be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<p>The data are in a common format and can be read using widely available software (open source or commercial).</p> <p>A comprehensive data format description was provided, together with instructions about how to read the data.</p> <p>The project has collected/generated 10 datasets. Their accessibility is in a common format and can be read using widely available software (open source or commercial).</p>

1.2.3 Making data interoperable

Questions	Answers
23 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?	The datasets used the trusted repository's basic metadata schema for administrative data, which is compliant with the recommended standards used by DataCite (https://search.datacite.org/) and OpenAIRE (https://www.basesearch.net/). For individual datasets, the following discipline specific vocabularies, standards, formats, and methodologies were used: e.g. GUM, and ISO 9001.
24 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or	The compatibility of our project-specific ontologies and vocabularies were guaranteed through appropriate mappings (glossary, alignment

vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow their re-use, refinement or extension?	tables, etc.) to more commonly used ontologies. The generated ontologies and vocabularies were published.
25 Will your data include qualified references ¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	Yes, the project's datasets that were deposited in the chosen repository (e.g. Zenodo) include qualified references to other datasets from previous research.

1.2.4 Increase data re-use

Questions	Answers
26 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?	A short README file (e.g. Markdown) were provided together with the data, in order to enable data analysis and to facilitate data re-use.
27 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	<p>The data has either been licensed under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights as set out in the Grant Agreement. Users were required to acknowledge the consortium and the source of the data in any resulting publications. Alternatively, the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication License (CC 0) were used.</p> <p>The project has collected/generated 10 datasets. Their licensing is CC BY 4.0 for all of them.</p>
28 Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<p>Any data published in open-access journals were usable by third parties after the datasets have been deposited in Zenodo. The data that do not relate to peer-reviewed publications were made available for re-use on a case-by-case basis.</p> <p>The project has collected/generated 9 datasets. Their usage is available by third parties, even after the end of the project, as they are all deposited in Zenodo or open repositories.</p>
29 Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Yes, the provenance and context of the data were thoroughly documented to meet relevant standards using the Provenance and Context Content Standard (PCCS) Matrix. Data were accompanied by information on how they were captured, processed, analysed, and validated. Other information that enables interpretation and use were also provided.
30 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	Data quality were assured through several quality assurance procedures: • Repeated and comparison measurements. • Adherence

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Questions	Answers
	to standards for data recording. • Use of controlled vocabularies and standard terminology. • Metrological characterisation of the measurement set-ups. • Validation of the data collected. • Provision of test results along with the data. • Peer-review of publications based on the data.
31 Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	<p><i>Allocation of resources</i></p> <p>The estimated curation and storage/preservation costs for making the data and research outputs FAIR are 12000 € (personnel costs). These costs were kept to a minimum by using i) suitable trusted repositories from the Registry of Research Data Repositories https://www.re3data.org/ where no additional costs are associated with long-term preservation, and ii) by making only relevant data and outputs FAIR. The estimated curation and storage/preservation costs are included in the project's budget and were claimed if compliant with the Grant Agreement's conditions.</p> <p><i>Security of other research outputs</i></p> <p>All participants are either accredited to, or work in compliance with, the ISO 17025 standard on the "General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories". The participants store other research outputs on their organisations' networks, which are protected by firewall, backups etc. Other research outputs are also stored in the project's SharePoint environment, with password-protected login. Deposition in public repositories provide additional security as they have multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis. This project do not generate sensitive other research outputs. The other research outputs were safely stored in open access repositories.</p> <p><i>Ethical aspects</i></p> <p>There are no ethical or legal issues.</p>

1.3 Other research outputs

Questions	Answers
32 In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).	<p>The new calibration methods, and protocols produced by the project were stored in the Protocol Exchange repository.</p> <p>The management of the IP issues surrounding the new materials that were developed in the project have been planned for in the project's consortium agreement. The consortium intends to seek patent protection.</p>
33 Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs were managed	As far as possible, the FAIR data approaches specified in questions 7-30 above were applied to the management of this project's other research outputs. This commitment were met by placing the new calibration methods, and protocols, in a repository and by patenting the new materials that were developed in the project in line with the requirements of the project's consortium agreement.

Questions	Answers
and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.	

1.4 Allocation of resources

Questions	Answers
34 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?	The estimated costs for making the data and other research outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) are 12 000 € (personnel costs). These costs have been kept to a minimum by using a free repository (Zenodo) and by making only relevant data and other outputs FAIR.
35 How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the European partnership on metrology grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).	The costs for making the data FAIR are included in the project's budget and were claimed if compliant with the Grant Agreement's conditions.
36 Who were responsible for data management in your project?	This consortium did not establish a DAC. The coordinator, with support from the participants, had overall responsibility for the management of data/research outputs and quality assurance. The coordinator was responsible for coordinating updates to the data management plan and for deciding on a case-by-case basis which data/research outputs were kept and for how long. The participant(s) that produced the data were responsible for organising backup and storage, archiving, and for depositing the data/research outputs within the chosen repositories.
37 How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data were kept and for how long)?	Long term preservation was ensured by depositing the data within repositories (Zenodo). There are no costs associated with the long-term preservation of the data in these repositories.

1.5 Data security

Questions	Answers
38 What provisions are or were in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	<p><i>Data recovery and secure storage</i></p> <p>All participants are either accredited to, or work in compliance with, the ISO 17025 standard on the "General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories". The participants store data on their organisations' networks, which are protected by firewall, backups etc. Data is also stored in the project's SharePoint environment, with password protected login.</p> <p>Deposition in the Zenodo public repository provide additional security as it has multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis.</p> <p><i>Transfer of sensitive data</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive data are only transferred in a depersonalised / deidentified or pseudonymised form.

39 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Yes, the data were safely stored in the Zenodo open access repository. Zenodo and the underlying Invenio Framework for digital repositories were designed according to the Open Archival Information Systems (OAIS) reference model. Zenodo is working towards ISO 16363 certification.
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1.6 Ethics

Questions	Answers
40 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics report(s) and the ethics section in the Annex 1.	There are no ethical or legal issues.
41 Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	The project does not deal with personal data.

1.7 Other issues

Questions	Answers
42 Do you, or will you, make use of other national / funder / sectorial / departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?	Data management was compliant to the research data policy of the funder: Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020 (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf)

2 Open science: research data management

Statement	Put an X in the box to confirm	Or, list any exceptions to this
All participants have adhered to the requirements of the project's GA and CA with respect to open science: research data management (GA Article 17 and its Annex 5) for this reporting period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	